

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES, AND PRACTICES IN RABIES PREVENTION AND MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Rabies continues to pose a significant public health challenge in the Philippines, particularly in regions like San Fernando, Pampanga. This study aimed to evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) regarding rabies prevention and management among residents of San Fernando. This study utilized a quantitative descriptive correlational research design. This study employed a stratified random sampling technique to ensure a representative sample of the population. The participants, aged 18 to 59 years, were systematically selected to gather a total of 400 respondents from the city of San Fernando located in the province of Pampanga. The results revealed significant gaps in knowledge and varying attitudes and practices towards rabies prevention. The results indicate a low level of knowledge on rabies, high level of attitude on rabies, and fair to high level of practices in addition, the association of these variables with that of their sociodemographic factors and KAP level was measured by Kruskal Wallis Test and Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test to explore the correlations between sociodemographic factors and KAP levels. The study's results underscored the need for targeted educational campaigns and community-based interventions to enhance rabies prevention efforts. These findings provide crucial insights for public health policymakers and practitioners aiming to reduce rabies incidence in San Fernando and similar settings.

Keywords: *rabies, public health, knowledge, attitudes, practices, prevention, management*

INTRODUCTION

In the Philippines, rabies remains a significant public health concern, with a considerable burden on human lives and the economy. The country is among the top rabies-endemic nations in Asia, with canine rabies being the primary source of human infections. Dogs, especially stray and unvaccinated pets, play a crucial role in the transmission of the virus. The Philippine Department of Health (DOH) has initiated several rabies control programs, including mass dog vaccination campaigns, educational initiatives, and efforts to make PEP available to those at risk. Despite these endeavors, rabies-related challenges persist.

Misconceptions about the virus, its transmission, and prevention strategies are common. Additionally, delays in seeking appropriate medical care after potential rabies exposure remain a significant problem (Miranda et al., 2017).

Within the Philippines, the province of Pampanga has faced its share of rabies related challenges. Pampanga, has been working on rabies control programs, including vaccination campaigns and awareness initiatives. However, local dynamics, such as dog populations, human-animal interactions, and cultural beliefs, can influence the prevalence of rabies and the success of control efforts (San Jose et al., 2020).

This research aims to address these knowledge gaps and provide essential insights into the knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to rabies exposure in the Philippines, in the province of Pampanga. Considering the local context and challenges, the study contributes to the broader national and international efforts to combat rabies while offering region-specific recommendations to improve rabies control in Pampanga.

Review of Related Literature

An estimated 59,000 people die from rabies each year, mostly in impoverished nations in Asia and Africa. Rabies is a neglected tropical illness (Hampson et al., 2015). The rabies virus attacks the neurological system and causes lethal encephalitis; a person infected with rabies dies as soon as clinical signs appear (Meslin & Briggs, 2013). Death is certain if clinical signs materialize, although the illness is avoidable if post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) is administered promptly following contact with a rabid animal (Salahuddin et al., 2016). It is the most lethal infectious disease, with a case rate close to 100% (Miranda et al., 2017). It is believed that mass dog vaccination (MDV) is the most economical way to stop rabies at its source because dog bites account for 90% of all rabies-related human deaths worldwide (Lankester et al., 2014).

Rabies is a neglected zoonotic illness that frequently goes unreported, especially in nations with little resources. Because of this, accurate data regarding the true frequency of human exposure to rabies remains limited, if not nonexistent, in third-world nations. It is thought that there is a severe underreporting of mortality worldwide, which has caused rabies to be considered a low-priority illness in many developing nations (Meslin & Briggs, 2013; Miranda et al., 2017). Domestic dogs are the main source of

rabies infection in Africa and Asia, where over 99% of instances of the disease in humans occur. Children under the age of 15 account for 45–60% of injuries sustained from dog bites and human fatalities (Meslin & Briggs, 2013). In both affluent and developing nations, children have a four-fold higher risk of being bitten than adults (Leung et al., 2007).

The Philippines is one of the top 10 nations in the world for the greatest number of fatal cases of rabies in humans (Miranda et al., 2017). According to the Rabies Prevention and Control Program, 2016, rabies is still widespread in the Philippines, where since 2012 there have been 635 occurrences of animal rabies (an average of 6.35 rabid canines per 100,000) and 200–300 human fatalities annually (an average of 2.13 deaths per million). The Philippine government has increased eradication measures aimed at the disease's canine source in an attempt to lessen its effects and eventually eradicate it in people. The Anti-Rabies Act of 2007 (Republic Act No. 9482) requires all provinces, cities, and municipalities to make sure that all canines have the required vaccinations and are registered. In addition, this entails bolstering surveillance and diagnostic labs for rabies, giving patients who have been bitten by animal's extra post exposure prophylaxis (PEP), and encouraging responsible pet ownership (RPO) (Republic of the Philippines- 13th Congress, 2007).

Poverty and poor awareness of rabies are generally associated with an increased vulnerability to the disease and are, consequently, major obstacles to prevention and control, especially in rural areas (Sabeta et al., 2022). Caretakers must be equipped with the necessary skills to prevent rabies and treat animal bites when they occur. This includes family members and medical experts.

A population that is knowledgeable about the risks of rabies and how to prevent it is essential to the effective implementation of any rabies program (Lembo et al., 2010). Inadequate health education initiatives lead to a deficiency of community awareness of the state of the illness and may result in improper wound care procedures during biting episodes. Instead of contacting medical experts, the majority of rural communities would visit traditional faith healers and employ traditional cures for bite wounds (Hergert & Nel, 2013). Even while not all bites result in rabies, individuals still need to be properly trained on the right first aid measures to take, like quickly cleaning bite wounds with soap, as this can significantly reduce the number of rabies deaths (Herbert et al., 2012)

Research Questions

The primary objective of this study was to comprehensively assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to rabies virus exposure prevention and management among the residents in San, Fernando, Pampanga.

Specifically, this sought to answer the following:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents as to:
 - 1.1. Age,
 - 1.2. Sex,

- 1.3. Barangay,
 - 1.4. Highest educational attainment,
 - 1.5. Family monthly income,
 - 1.6. Number of Pets,
 - 1.7. Type of Pets,
 - 1.8. Have you or your family experienced animal bites?
 - 1.9. Have you attended any awareness activity related to rabies?
2. What is the level of knowledge of respondents on rabies prevention and management?
 3. What is the level of attitude of respondents on rabies prevention and management?
 4. What is the level of practice of respondents on rabies prevention and management?
 5. What is the difference in the level of knowledge, attitude, and practice of respondents on rabies prevention and management when grouped according to demographic characteristics?
 6. What is the significant relationship between the respondents' level of knowledge, attitude, and practices on rabies prevention and management?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design used in this study was a cross-sectional research design. This study examined the impact of the participants' demographic profile on the level of knowledge, of what kind of attitudes and practices on pet management towards the prevention and control of rabies virus.

Participants and Setting

The researchers used a stratified sampling technique in quantitative investigations using survey instruments in which a type of probability sampling where the researchers did a proportionate sampling (annex sample per barangay) and used barangays as strata. Systematic random sampling was then used for the identification of actual respondents. The survey was conducted in the city of San Fernando located in the province of Pampanga. The city is divided into 6 RHUs with a total of 35 barangays.

With a population of 370,274 as of 2024, 400 respondents were collected with a minimum sample size of 384 San Fernando residents calculated using the sample size computation estimating proportion with a 95% confidence level, 5% margin of error, and 50% response distribution.

The selected participants were informed of the study's purpose and that their participation was voluntary. The data collected from participants were used to meet the study's goal of improving rabies virus exposure prevention and management's knowledge, attitudes, and practices.

Research Instruments

This study used a questionnaire that is designed to identify factors that influence the level of the participant's knowledge, attitudes, and practices on rabies prevention and management. The questionnaire was adapted based on previously similar studies (Bundalian et al., 2020). Permission to use the research tool was secured and granted by the author.

For the first part of the questionnaire demographic profiles were obtained.

The second part of the questionnaire deals with knowledge about rabies consisting of 21 questions assessed through yes-or-no, true-or-false, and selects all that apply and attitudes about rabies consisting of 7 questions using a Likert scale of 1-4.

The third part of the questionnaire contains 9 items about the information National Law Number 9482 using yes-or-no and correct and incorrect questions. And knowledge about proper dog/cat care is composed of 9 items.

The fourth part of the questionnaire is about attitudes toward responsible dog ownership consisting of 6 questions using a Likert scale of 1-4 and Practices for responsible pet owners using yes-or-no questions that were composed of 13 items. Adjectival interpretation of knowledge, attitude, and practices was interpreted using Bloom's cut which may be as follows:

Adjectival interpretation of knowledge, attitude, and practices was interpreted using Bloom's cut which may be as follows:

Domain	80-10%	60-79%	Less than 60%
Knowledge	High Level of Knowledge	Moderate or fair Level of Knowledge	Low Level of Knowledge
Attitude	Positive Attitude	Neutral Attitude	Negative Attitude
Practice	Good Level of Practice	Neutral Level of Practice	Negative Level of Practice

Data Gathering Procedure

A standardized survey questionnaire was the guide of the researchers. The researcher conducted a one-on-one personal survey to obtain the necessary data. The survey questionnaire was self-administered however the researchers guided the respondents while answering. Before the survey, the respondents were asked to sign consent forms. To make it simpler for respondents and researchers to provide data, the questionnaire was distributed via a pen-and-paper method.

Statistical Treatment of Data/Analysis of Information

Google Sheets and Microsoft Excel were used for data encoding in this study. To provide a thorough overview of the survey results, descriptive statistics was utilized to compute the means, standard deviations, and ranges for every question.

Bloom's cut-off point was used to determine the levels of knowledge, attitudes, and practices of the respondents. Additionally, the Kruskal Wallis Test and Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test were used to compare the knowledge, attitude, and practices across demographic variables, correlational analysis was used to look into the relationships between different survey questions. Spearman's rho was also used to evaluate the strength and direction of relationships between various variables.

RESULTS

A total of 400 respondents participated in the study. The sample size was determined based on the stratum, and barangay. Barangays with the larger population have larger sample sizes. Barangay Calulut has the highest number of respondents with 47, comprising 11.75%, followed by Bulaon with 30 respondents (7.50%), San Agustin with 24 respondents (6.00%), and Dolores with 23 respondents (5.75%). Other barangays have respondents ranging from 1 to 18.

Table 1.1 Distribution of respondents across barangay

Barangay	Frequency	Percent
Dolores	23	5.75
Juliana	5	1.25
Lourdes	5	1.25
Santo Rosario	1	0.25
San Jose	18	4.50
Santa Teresita	1	0.25
Santo Nino	12	3.00
Del Carmen	8	2.00
Magliman	7	1.75
Maimpis	13	3.25
Quebiauan	11	2.75
San Agustin	24	6.00

Bulaon	30	7.50
Calulut	47	11.75
Malpitic	9	2.25
Alasas	9	2.25
San Isidro	11	2.75
Del Rosario	9	2.25
Dela Paz Norte	8	2.00
Dela Paz Sur	6	1.50
Saguin	9	2.25
Lara	5	1.25
Del Pilar	14	3.50
Pandaras	2	0.50
San Felipe	6	1.50
San Juan	7	1.75
San Nicolas	11	2.75
San Pedro	14	3.50
Santa Lucia	11	2.75
Baliti	8	2.00
Malino	6	1.50
Panipuan	9	2.25
Pulungbulu	7	1.75
Sindalan	17	4.25
Telabastagan	17	4.25

Table 1.2 presents the distribution of respondents according to their demographic characteristics. The majority were in the age 25 years old to 34 years old (35.75%), and more than half were males (53.75%). In terms of educational attainment, most of the respondents were high school graduates (47.00%), followed by college graduates (32.50%). Most were in a lower income bracket with income of below Php 10,000 to Php 19,999 monthly (44.00%), followed by those with income of Php 20,000 to Php 39,999 monthly (36.00%). There were 82 (20.50%) who do not have pets, while the majority have 2 pets (24.75%), followed by those with 3 pets (22.75%). More than half own a cat (55.25%), while 33.25% own a dog. Almost 70% have at least one (1) family member who has been bitten by an animal. Moreover, 52.25% attended awareness seminars on rabies.

Table 1.2 Demographic characteristics of respondents

Demographic Variable	Frequency	Percent
Age (in years)		
18-24	100	25.00
25-34	143	35.75
35-44	98	24.50
45-54	45	11.25
55-59	14	3.50
Sex		
Male	215	53.75
Female	185	46.25
Educational Attainment		
Elementary	82	20.50
High school	188	47.00
College	130	32.50
Monthly income		
Below 10,000-19,999	176	44.00
20,000-39,999	144	36.00
40,000-79,999	65	16.25
80,000 and above	15	3.75
Number of pets		
0	82	20.50
1	79	19.75
2	99	24.75
3	91	22.75
4	23	5.75
5	25	6.25
6	0	0.00
7	1	0.25
Type of pets_		

0	82	20.50
Cat	221	55.25
Dog	133	33.25
Cow	1	0.25
Others	1	0.25
any member of your family been bitten by an animal		
Yes	278	69.50
None	122	30.50
attended rabies awareness activities		
Yes	209	52.25
No	191	47.75

The respondent's answers to the statement regarding knowledge of rabies are shown in **Table 2.1**. There were 83% who had heard of rabies, however, there were still 68 (17%) who still had not heard about it. The majority believe that rabies is not caused by a virus (53.50%), which is incorrect. The majority (85.00%) said that cats can be rabid, 67.00% believe that bats can be a source of rabies, and 73.50% said that snakes do not have rabies, which were all correct answers. Slightly more than half of the respondents believe that rabies can be acquired through inhalation (51.25%), through bites of mosquitos or other insects (53.50%), and by eating the meat of dogs with rabies (61.00%), which were all false. Additionally, around 86% believe that rabies can be acquired by animals and humans through bite. And 55.75% believe that it can be acquired when licked or scratched by an animal with rabies.

Only slightly more than 50% said that rabies is fatal. On the other hand, 77.00% were correct that the animal with rabies drools, and 58% were correct in believing that an animal with rabies is not quiet or kind. In terms of rabies prevention, 61.00% were correct in believing that rabies can be prevented by vaccination and that tethering or confining pets so it does not wander prevents the spread of rabies (70.75%). However, 61.75% also believe that it can be prevented by killing stray dogs and cats, by neutering and removing the uterus (49.75%), and by killing unvaccinated dogs and cats (58.75%). On managing animal bites, 73.75% know that it should be washed thoroughly using soap and water, and 53.50% believe that it is incorrect to seek medical treatment from an albularyo.

On average, the respondents scored 12.37 out of 20 points on the question of knowledge of rabies. This is only 61.85% of the score.

Table 2.1. Responses on knowledge of rabies

Statement	Yes		No	
	n	%	n	%
Have heard of rabies	83.00		17.00	
Statement	Correct		Incorrect	
	n	%	n	%
Rabies is caused by a virus	186	46.50	214	53.50
Cats can be rabid	340	85.00	60	15.00
Bats can be the source of rabies	268	67.00	132	33.00
The snake can be the source of rabies	106	26.50	294	73.50
Rabies can be acquired by animals and humans by inhaling the air	205	51.25	195	48.75
Rabies can be acquired by animals and humans through the bite of mosquitoes and other insects	214	53.50	186	46.50
Rabies can be acquired by animals and humans through the bite of an animal with rabies	343	85.75	57	14.25
Rabies can be acquired by animals and humans when licked or scratched by an animal with rabies	223	55.75	177	44.25
Rabies can be acquired by animals and humans by eating the meat of dogs with rabies	244	61.00	156	39.00
Rabies is incurable and fatal	214	53.50	186	46.50
An animal with rabies drools	308	77.00	92	23.00
The animal with rabies is quiet and kind	168	42.00	232	58.00
Rabies can be prevented and prevented from spreading by vaccinating pet dogs and cats	244	61.00	156	39.00

Rabies can be prevented and prevented from spreading by killing stray dogs and cats	247	61.75	153	38.25
Rabies can be prevented and prevented from spreading by neutering the male dog/cat and removing the uterus from the female dog/cat	199	49.75	201	50.25
Rabies can be prevented and prevented from spreading by killing unvaccinated dogs and cats	235	58.75	165	41.25
Tethering or confining the pet dog/cat so that it does not wander will help prevent rabies	283	70.75	117	29.25
When bitten by an animal with rabies, the wound should be washed thoroughly with soap and water	295	73.75	105	26.25
When bitten by an animal with rabies, it is important to seek medical treatment from an albularyo	186	46.50	214	53.50

Mean score = 12.37

Table 2.2 shows the source of the respondents on their knowledge of rabies. About one-third (1/3) of the respondents learned about rabies from schools. This is followed by the 15.50% who knew rabies from a neighbor or stories of friends, 14.00% who learned from the newspaper, and 12.75% who knew since they saw a person or animal with rabies.

Table 2.2. Source of knowledge about rabies

How or where did you get the knowledge about rabies	Frequency	Percent
School	134	33.50
Television	35	8.75
Radio	24	6.00
Newspaper	56	14.00
Magazine/ Comics	8	2.00
Neighbor/ Friend story	62	15.50
Saw a person or animal with rabies	51	12.75

Seminar in the barangay or elsewhere	25	6.25
Doctor	5	1.25

Table 2.3 presents the responses on knowledge about Rabies Law. Only 40.25% know any laws on the suppression of rabies. However, when asked, 68% know that registration of pet dog is required to determine if it is vaccinated or not, 79.50% know that a dog owner who does not vaccinate and register the pet can be fined, 71.50% knows that an owner who does not leash the pet every time it is taken out of the yard will have to pay a fine, 84% knows that it is forbidden to slaughter a dog and eat or sell its meat, and 77.50% knows that anyone caught selling dog meat will have to pay a corresponding fine.

On the other hand, only 28.75% believe that an owner who refuses to lock up to observe the pet after it bites will be fined, and only 31% know that an owner who refuses to lock up to observe the pet after it bites and does not bear the cost of treating the victim will have to pay the corresponding fine, and only 40% knows that anyone caught selling dog meat can be punished with imprisonment.

Overall, the average score of the respondents on the knowledge on Rabies Law is 5.21 out of 9 points. This corresponds to 57.89% of the total score.

Table 2.3. Responses on knowledge about National Law No. 9482

Statement	Yes		No	
	n	%	n	%
Do you know any laws regarding suppression of rabies?	161	40.25	239	59.75
Statement	Correct		Incorrect	
	n	%	n	%
Registration of the pet dog is required to determine if it is vaccinated or not.	272	68.00	128	32.00
The dog owner who does not vaccinate and register the pet can be punished by being fined.	318	79.50	82	20.50
The owner of the dog who does not leash the pet every time it is taken out of the yard will have to pay the corresponding fine.	286	71.50	114	28.50

It is forbidden to slaughter a dog and eat or sell its meat.

336 84.00 64 16.00

The owner of the dog who refuses to lock up to observe the pet after it bites must be fined.

115 28.75 285 71.25

The owner of the dog who refuses to lock up to observe the pet after it bites and does not bear the cost of treating the victim will have to pay the corresponding fine.

124 31.00 276 69.00

Anyone caught selling dog meat can be punished with imprisonment.

160 40.00 240 60.00

Anyone caught selling dog meat will have to pay a corresponding fine.

310 77.50 90 22.50

Mean score = 5.21

Table 2.4 presents the responses of the participants on the knowledge on responsible pet ownership. There were 81.75% who believe that proper dog care helps prevent the spread of rabies. Furthermore, more than 80% of the respondents answered —True that the owner should give food to their pets, take them to the vet, ensure that it does not soil anywhere, inform authorities when their pet bites, and confine or tie the pet to be observed, and to ensure the pet has vaccination record. On the other hand, more than 60% said that it is true that the owner should let his pets roam, and that the owner must immediately cut off the pet's head to take it to the laboratory when it bites.

On the average, the respondents got 7.17 out of 9 questions. This corresponds to 79.67% of the total, which is the highest compared to the knowledge on rabies, and knowledge on Rabies Law.

Table 2.4. Responses on knowledge about responsible pet ownership has a vaccination record

Statement	Yes		No	
	n	%	n	%
Proper dog care helps prevent the spread of rabies	81.75		73	18.25
Statement	True		False	
	n	%	n	%

The dog/cat owner lets his pets roam	263	65.75	137	34.25
The owner of the dog/cat gives food to his pet	338	84.50	62	15.50
The owner takes the pet dog/cat to the vet when it is sick	334	83.50	66	16.50
The owner of the dog/cat ensures that the pet does not soil itself anywhere	335	83.75	65	16.25
When the pet dog/cat bites, the owner informs the authorities	335	83.75	65	16.25
When a pet dog/cat bites, the owner is advised to confine or tie the pet so that it can be observed	321	80.25	79	19.75
The owner of the dog/cat ensures that the pet has a vaccination record	347	86.75	53	13.25
When a pet dog/cat bites, the owner must immediately cut off the pet's head to take it to the laboratory	267	66.75	133	33.25
Mean score= 7.17				

The summary of the distribution of the level of knowledge is shown in **Table 2.5**. On the knowledge of rabies, only 12.00% have good knowledge, 49.00% have fair knowledge, and 39.00% have low knowledge. On the knowledge of Rabies Law, 70.75% have low knowledge, 13.50% have moderate knowledge, and only 15.75% have good knowledge of the law. On the other hand, the majority (47.25%) have good knowledge of responsible pet ownership, 32.25% have fair knowledge, and 20.50% have low knowledge.

Table 2.5. Level of knowledge on rabies

Knowledge on Rabies Prevention and Management	Good	Fair	Low
Knowledge on rabies	48 (12.00%)	196 (49.00%)	156 (39.00%)
Knowledge on rabies law	63 (15.75%)	54 (13.50%)	283 (70.75%)

	189	129	82
Knowledge on responsible pet ownership	(47.25%)	(32.25%)	(20.50%)

Table 3.1 shows the responses of participants on their attitude toward rabies. More than 80% said definitely yes that they would inform authorities and get medical treatment if bitten by a stray dog or cat. Moreover, 70% and above answered definitely yes to informing authorities and seeking treatment if scratched by a stray dog or cat, and informing the person in charge if there is a suspected case of rabies in our community. The majority also will inform authorities and get medical treatment if bitten by a pet dog or cat (62.25%), and will kill not the stray dog/cat suspected of having rabies (58.25%). More than 70% also believe it is important to stop the dog population from growing, and that they are willing to help the campaign against rabies.

In summary, the respondents will inform authorities if bitten or scratched by a stray or pet dog/cat, will inform the person in charge, believes that it is important to stop the population of dogs from growing, and are willing to help in the campaign against rabies (median of 4 which is equivalent to definitely yes). Moreover, respondents will not kill stray dog/cat suspected of having rabies.

Table 3.1. Responses on attitudes about rabies

Statement	Definitely Yes	Probably Yes	Probably No	Definitely No	Median
I will inform the authorities and get medical treatment if bitten by a stray dog or cat.	334 (83.50%)	62 (15.50%)	4 (1.00%)	0 (0.00%)	4
I will inform the authorities and get medical treatment if bitten by my pet dog or cat.	249 (62.25%)	144 (36.00%)	7 (1.75%)	0 (0.00%)	4
I will inform the authorities	314 (78.50%)	77 (19.25%)	9 (2.25%)	0 (0.00%)	4

and I will seek treatment if scratched by a stray dog or cat.

I will inform the person in charge if there is a suspected case of rabies in our community. **280 (70.00%)** **97 (24.25%)** **20 (5.00%)** **3 (0.75%)** **4**

I will kill the stray dog/cat suspected of having rabies. **47 (11.75%)** **11 (2.75%)** **109 (27.25%)** **233 (58.25%)** **4**

I believe it is important to stop the dog population from growing. **292 (73.00%)** **89 (22.25%)** **10 (2.50%)** **9 (2.25%)** **4**

I am willing to help the campaign against rabies. **284 (71.00%)** **111 (27.75%)** **5 (1.25%)** **0 (0.00%)** **4**

1-definitely no, 2-probably no, 3-probably yes, 4-definitely yes

Table 3.2 shows the responses of the participants on attitudes about responsible pet ownership. Most of the respondents agree on tying their dogs (56.75%). The majority, on the other hand, agree to pay just to have their pets vaccinated (57.00%), and that tying or confining a pet is a cruel act (49.00%). The responses are distributed on statements such as only vaccinating their pets if it is free of charge (33.25% totally agree, and 33.25% disagree), recommending their pet for spaying or neutering (24.75% totally agree, 33.25% disagree, and 20.75% totally disagree), and on dogs/cats being allowed to give birth and breed (31.75% totally agree, and 33.75% disagree).

Table 3.2. Responses on attitudes about responsible pet ownership

Statement	Totally agree	Agree	Disagree	Totally disagree	Median
I'm fine with tying or snarling my dog	227 (56.75%)	171 (42.75%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.50%)	4
I am willing to pay just to have my pet vaccinated against rabies	167 (41.75%)	228 (57.00%)	4 (1.00%)	1 (0.25%)	3
I will only vaccinate my pet dog/cat if it is free of charge	133 (33.25%)	51 (12.75%)	133 (33.25%)	83 (20.75%)	3
I recommend having my pet dog/cat spayed or deuterated	99 (24.75%)	92 (23.00%)	129 (32.25%)	80 (20.00%)	3
Tying or confining a pet dog/cat is a cruel act	146 (36.50%)	196 (49.00%)	12 (3.00%)	46 (11.50%)	2
Dogs and cats should be allowed to give birth and breed	127 (31.75%)	53 (13.25%)	135 (33.75%)	85 (21.25%)	2

1-totally disagree, 2-disagree, 3-agree, 4-totally agree

The level of attitude toward rabies is presented in **Table 3.3**. There were 84.50% who had a good or positive attitude toward rabies, and 15.50% had a fair attitude. On responsible pet ownership, the majority of the respondents have a fair attitude (87.25%), while 12.75% have low knowledge; no respondent had a good attitude on responsible pet ownership.

Table 3.3. Level of attitude on rabies

KAP on Rabies	Good	Fair	Low
Attitude on rabies	338 (84.50%)	62 (15.50%)	0 (0.00%)
Attitude on responsible pet ownership	0 (0.00%)	349 (87.25%)	51 (12.75%)

Table 4.1 shows the practices of dog owners on responsible pet ownership. The majority vaccinate their dogs every year (88.24%), said that their pet is always on a leash (91.86%), said that they leash them when out in the yard (93.21%), and feed them every day (91.86%). The majority also do not let their pet dog roam (69.68%). On the other hand, the majority said that their dog is not always locked up (57.01%).

On average, out of six (6) total points, dog owners have a mean score of 4.78 on responsible pet ownership on their pet dogs.

Table 4.1. Responses on practices about responsible pet ownership among dog owners

Statement	Yes	%	No	%
I vaccinate my pet dog every year	195	88.24	26	11.76
My pet dog is always on a leash	203	91.86	18	8.14
I leash my pet dog when I take it out of the yard	206	93.21	15	6.79
My pet dog is always locked up.	95	42.99	126	57.01
I let my pet dog roam.	67	30.32	154	69.68
I feed my pet dog every day.	203	91.86	18	8.14
Mean score = 4.78				

The practices of cat owners on their pets are shown in **Table 4.2**. Contrary to dog owners, the majority of cat owners do not vaccinate their cats (58.22%), and they let their cats roam (70.37%). On the other hand, most of them keep their cats locked (66.67%), on a leash (60.00%), and feed them every day (91.11%).

On average, out of five (5), the mean practice score of cat owners on responsible ownership is 2.89.

Table 4.2. Responses on practices about responsible pet ownership among cat owners

Statement	Yes	%	No	%
I vaccinate my pet cat every year	56	41.48	79	58.52
My pet cat is always locked up	90	66.67	45	33.33
My pet cat is always on a leash	81	60.00	54	40.00
I let my pet cat roam.	95	70.37	40	29.63
I feed my pet cat every day.	123	91.11	12	8.89
Mean score = 2.89				

Presented in **Table 4.3** are the responses of pet owners (dog, cat, or other pets). The majority do not have a vaccination record for their pets (54.26%), but most of them take their pets to the vet whenever they are sick (82.65%). When asked the reason why they are not vaccinating their pets, most of them answered that their pet dog or cat is not at home or wandering when the vaccinator arrives (20.59%), they do not know any vaccination schedule (19.12%), that there is no time or season to vaccinate their pets (18.38%), and that they cannot touch their cats (16.18%).

Table 4.3. Responses on practices about responsible pet ownership among pet owners

Statement	n	%
I have the vaccination record of my pet dog/cat		
Yes		
No	145	45.74
I take my pet to the vet when he is sick.		
Yes		
No	262	82.65
Mean score = 1.28		
Reason for not vaccinating your pet		
can't handle the dog		
can't touch the cat	17	12.50
	22	16.18

there is no time/season to vaccinate the pet	25	18.38
do not know that there is a vaccination schedule in place	26	19.12
the dog/cat is not at home or wandering when the vaccinator arrives	28	20.59
the dog/cat is not yet at the right age to be vaccinated	11	8.09
had a bad experience vaccinating a pet	6	4.41
It is not known whether the cat should be vaccinated	1	0.74

The summary of the practice of pet ownership among dog, cat, and pet owners is shown in **Table 4.4**. Among the dog owners, the majority have good practice (69.23%), with 21.27% having fair practice and 9.50% having low practice. For the cat owners, the majority have fair practice (45.93%), followed by those with low practice (34.81%), and only 19.26% have good practice on responsible pet ownership. Among the pet owners, 62.78% have fair practice, 32.81% have good practice, and 4.42% have low practice scores.

Table 4.4. Summary of practices on pet ownership

Practice on responsible pet ownership	Good	Fair	Low
Among dog owners	153 (69.23%)	47 (21.27%)	21 (9.50%)
Among cat owners	26 (19.26%)	62 (45.93%)	47 (34.81%)
Among pet owners	104 (32.81%)	199 (62.78%)	14 (4.42%)

The difference of the respondents on the knowledge, attitude, and practice of rabies is presented in **Table 5**. Differences were tested across different demographic variables. There is a difference in the knowledge on rabies across age ($p=0.0006$), barangay ($p=0.0001$), monthly income ($p=0.0001$), number of pets ($p=0.0001$), and whether there is a history of animal bite in the family or none ($p=0.0161$). Furthermore, there is a difference in the attitude toward rabies between males and females ($p=0.0109$), across barangay ($p=0.0001$), monthly income ($p=0.0001$), number of pets ($p=0.0001$), history of animal bite ($p=0.0055$), and if they have attended any awareness activity on rabies or not ($p=0.0005$).

A significant difference in knowledge on rabies law was seen across all demographic variables except age group

On the knowledge on responsible pet ownership, only the sex ($p=0.0035$),

barangay ($p=0.0001$), monthly income ($p=0.0001$), number of pets ($p=0.0001$), and attendance on any awareness activity on rabies ($p= <0.0001$). Moreover, on the attitude toward responsible pet ownership, there is a significant difference across all variables except for sex and attending any awareness activity on rabies

On practices on responsible pet ownership among dog owners, a significant difference was found except across sex, educational attainment, and having attended awareness on rabies. On the practice of RPO among the cat owners, only barangay ($p=0.0001$), monthly income ($p=0.0023$), number of pets ($p=0.0351$), and attendance on rabies awareness activities ($p=<0.0001$) have a significant difference. Lastly, there is a difference on the RPO of pet owners across the demographic variables' barangay ($p=0.0001$), educational attainment ($p=0.0465$), monthly income ($p=0.0003$), number of pets ($p=0.0002$), history of animal bite in the family ($p=0.0011$), and attendance on rabies awareness activities ($p=0.0408$).

Table 5. Difference on the level of knowledge, attitude, and practice of respondents on rabies prevention and management

KAP on Rabies	Age	Sex	Barangay	Educational Attainment	Monthly Income	No. of Pets	History of animal bite in the family	Attended awareness activity on rabies
Knowledge on rabies	0.0006*	0.9790	0.0001*	0.0300	0.0001*	0.0001*	0.0161*	0.2898
Attitude on rabies	0.8474	0.0050	0.0001*	0.0001*	0.0001*	0.0001*	0.0004*	0.0120*
Knowledge on rabies law	0.0565	0.0035*	0.0001*	0.1367	0.0001*	0.0001*	0.2184	<0.0001*
Knowledge on responsible pet ownership	0.0002*	0.2777	0.0001*	0.0001*	0.0001*	0.0013	0.0031*	0.8098
Attitude on responsible pet ownership	0.0187*	0.5261	0.0001*	0.8351	0.0001*	0.0001*	0.0195*	0.3227
Practice on responsible cat ownership	0.1998	0.5739	0.0001*	0.3976	0.0023*	0.0351*	0.2270	<0.0001*
Practice on responsible pet ownership	0.5861	0.4380	0.0001*	0.0465*	0.0003*	0.0002*	0.0011*	0.0408*

*significant at 0.05 level

Table 6 shows the pairwise relationship of the knowledge, attitude, and practices of the respondents. There is a significant relationship across knowledge on rabies, rabies law, and responsible pet ownership. Knowledge on rabies and rabies law has a positive relationship, while a negative relationship was observed on the relationship of knowledge on RPO and rabies, and knowledge on RPO and rabies law.

Moreover, knowledge on rabies, its law, and RPO, and attitudes on rabies and responsible pet ownership have a significant relationship except for knowledge on rabies law and attitude toward responsible pet ownership (p is not less than 0.05). Again, two pairs have a negative relationship: knowledge on rabies and attitude toward rabies, and knowledge on rabies law and attitude toward rabies.

Practice on pet ownership across dog owners all have a relationship on knowledge and attitudes, with all relationships being positive. This means that having a higher knowledge and attitude on rabies corresponds to higher practice. In the practice of cat owners, there is only a significant association with knowledge, with knowledge on responsible ownership having a negative relationship. Lastly, for pet owners, only the knowledge of RPO, attitude on rabies, and attitude on pet ownership have a relationship with the practices on pet ownership. There is also a negative relationship on knowledge of RPO and its practice among pet owners

Table 6. Relationship of the respondent's level of knowledge, attitude, and practices on rabies prevention and management

	Knowledge on Rabies	Knowledge on rabies law	Knowledge on responsible pet ownership	Attitude on Rabies	Attitude on responsible pet ownership
Knowledge on rabies	$r=0.3025^*$ $p=<0.0001$				
Attitude on rabies	$r=-0.1180^*$ $p=0.0182$	$r=-0.1178^*$ $p=0.0184$			
Knowledge on rabies law	$r=-0.2251^*$ $p=<0.0001$	$r=-0.2033^*$ $p=<0.0001$	$r=0.7927^*$ $p=$		
Knowledge on responsible pet ownership	$r=0.1773^*$ $p=0.0004$	$r=0.0660$ $p=0.1875$	$r=0.3739^*$ $p=<0.0001$	$r=0.2827^*$ $p=<0.0001$	
Attitude on responsible pet ownership	$r=0.2626^*$ $p=0.0001$	$r=0.4043^*$ $p=<0.0001$	$r=0.3855^*$ $p=<0.0001$	$r=0.6930^*$ $p=<0.0001$	$r=0.6931^*$ $p=<0.0001$
Practice on responsible cat ownership	$r=0.1792^*$ $p=0.0391$	$r=0.2435^*$ $p=0.0047$	$r=-0.2419^*$ $p=0.0050$	$r=0.0125$ $p=0.8863$	$r=-0.0179$ $p=0.8378$

Practice on responsible pet ownership	r=0.0750 p=0.1841	r=0.0470 p=0.4057	r=-0.3142* p=<0.0001	r=-0.3796* p=<0.0001	r=-0.2516* p=<0.0001
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r – Spearman’s rho; p – p-value
*significant at 0.05 level

DISCUSSION

Rabies is one of the major public health problems in the Philippines due to its acute fatality. According to The World Health Organization (WHO), the Philippines is one of the top ten countries fighting the disease. Therefore, sufficient knowledge and appropriate attitudes and practices are very crucial when it comes to rabies prevention and management. The Department of Health (DOH) in the Philippines established a Rabies Prevention and Control Program with a national vision of becoming a —rabies free country by the year 2022. This study explored the current pet owners’ KAP from the City of San Fernando, Pampanga, Philippines.

The Level of Knowledge of the Respondents Regarding Rabies Prevention and Management

The result of this study supports the assumption that the level of knowledge of a person contributes to the risk of being unable to prevent and manage the spread of the rabies virus. In terms of knowledge of rabies, a mean score of 12.37 was identified. Most of the respondents (49.00%) have a fair knowledge of rabies followed by low (39.00%) levels, and only (12.00%) have good knowledge. The lack of official and reliable sources—such as health, veterinary, and educational authorities—of general information on the disease may be the cause of this alarmingly low level of awareness. Additionally, educational initiatives still fall short of ideal standards even in Maputo and Matola’s urban regions (Salomao et al., 2014).

Moreover, a mean score of 7.17 was identified about the participants’ knowledge of responsible pet ownership. The majority of the respondents (47.25%) have good knowledge, followed by fair (32.25%), and low knowledge (20.50%). A study in Magalang, Pampanga showed similar results. In Magalang, there was no structured awareness campaign on rabies and RPO; nonetheless, animal technicians use vaccination programs as a chance to tell pet owners about their duties and to teach them about the prevention and control of rabies (San Jose et al., 2020).

The Level of Attitude of the Respondents Regarding Rabies Prevention and Management

Furthermore, the result also supports the association between the level of attitude and rabies virus prevention and management. Most of them (84.5%) showed a positive

attitude toward rabies and fairness (15.50%). On the other hand, the majority of the respondents (87.25%) have a fair attitude and a low (12.75%) attitude toward responsible pet ownership. Correlating this observation with that of the knowledge level, even though the knowledge of the participants regarding rabies and rabies law is low to a fair level, the knowledge in terms of responsible pet ownership is good or high which also showed a relationship towards their attitude. Therefore, their knowledge of responsible pet ownership was applied to their attitude. According to Dandan Li et al. (2021), in the perspective of almost 90% of participants, rabies vaccination needs to be administered as quickly as feasible following a suspected rabid bite. This positive outlook is consistent with the World Health Organization's rabies guidelines, which state that individuals should get medical help right away if they believe an animal they may have bitten is rabid (WHO, 2010). The majority of respondents said that rabies may be stopped in its tracks by immunizing vulnerable cats and dogs. This positive outlook might persuade pet owners to vaccinate their cats or dogs, which would lessen the likelihood that every bite is caused by a rabid animal and aid in the quest to eradicate rabies (Taylor et al., 2017).

The Level of Practices of the Respondents Regarding Rabies Prevention and Management

Moreover, the result of this supports the assumption that the level of practices contributes to the risk of spreading the rabies virus. In determining the appropriateness of the practice, the results showed that although the majority of the dog owners have good practice (69.23%) in terms of responsible pet ownership in comparison to those who have fair (21.27%), and (9.50%) having low practice, it is still crucial to consider different factors that influence the success of population management because as what the result showed, there are still people who demonstrated fair to low practices in responsible pet ownership. The growth in the number of free-roaming dogs is attributed to both abandoned and unrestricted-owned dogs. The management of free-roaming dog populations may be hindered by dog ownership policies that permit owners' dogs to roam and do not restrict breeding. Dog population control practitioners need to ascertain how much owned dogs contribute to the population of free-roaming dogs to customize management actions such as encouraging responsible ownership through legislation and education programs (World Organization of Animal Health OIE, 2019; Smith et al., 2022).

On the other hand, for the cat owners, contrary to the dog owners, the majority have fair (45.93%), with 34.81% having low practice, and only 19.26% having good practice on responsible pet ownership. A study in Magalang, Pampanga showed similar results. 66.1% of the 168 cat owners practiced moderately, 14.9% practiced well, and 15.5% practiced poorly. Dog owners made up the majority of individuals who followed appropriate pet ownership practices. Unaccountable pet owners continued to allow their cats—of which there are still most—to go free and urinate and defecate almost anywhere. It showed that dog owners demonstrate better practice in terms of responsible pet ownership than cat owners (San Jose et al., 2020). This discrepancy may also be due to the differences in the knowledge and perceptions about different pets, as well as

the educational attainment of the pet owners. Furthermore, the results on the practices among pet owners showed that the majority of the participants have fair (62.78%) practice, with 32.81% having good practice, while only 4.42% have low practice scores.

Differences in the level of knowledge, attitude, and practice of respondents on rabies prevention and management

Differences were tested across different demographic variables. A significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between all demographic variables of the respondents and their level of knowledge has been established in this study except for sex, educational attainment, and attended awareness activity on knowledge. Furthermore, all variables except age have significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in their knowledge of rabies law. In terms of their knowledge of responsible pet ownership, all variables except age, educational attainment, and history of animal bites in the family are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

On the other hand, there is a significant difference ($p < 0.5$) between all demographic variables and their attitude on rabies except age, and educational attainment. A significant difference ($p < 0.05$) has been established between all demographic variables between attitude toward responsible pet ownership except sex and attended awareness activity on rabies.

Moreover, the practice of responsible dog ownership has a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) with all the variables except sex, educational attainment, and attended awareness of rabies. In addition, there is also a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between demographic variables and practice on responsible cat ownership except for age, sex, educational attainment, and history of animal bites in the family. Lastly, practices on responsible pet ownership have significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between demographic variables except age, and sex.

In this light factor should be taken into account when planning for interventions toward successful rabies prevention and management in the city. **Age** is linked with their level of knowledge of rabies ($p = 0.0006$), attitude toward responsible pet ownership ($p = 0.0002$), and practice of responsible dog ownership ($p = 0.0187$). The younger age respondents with higher education and social status were found more knowledgeable than their counterparts in terms of knowledge variables, including the cause of rabies, mode of transmission, clinical signs, treatment, and preventive measures of this fatal disease (Pushkar Pal et al., 2021). The older age (≥ 36 years) was likely to know less about different preventive measures (Jemberu et al., 2013). However, older populations in India were found to have higher levels of knowledge than younger populations in earlier studies (Tripathy et al., 2017). A notably greater proportion of participants, aged between 20 and 39, were identified as having a strong knowledge of RDO. One possible explanation for this could be that younger generations have greater access to information sources than older generations. Among those favorable attitudes, the majority of the participants were aged 20 to 39 years old. Younger people are more likely to conduct responsible pet ownership than older people, and their thought patterns may differ from others, leading to more positive attitudes. The younger people in this age

group have a higher level of understanding regarding the use of crucial pet care practices including vaccination and breeding control. (De Silva & Kumarapeli, 2021).

Statistical results also showed that **Sex** has a significant difference with knowledge of rabies law ($p=0.0050$), knowledge of responsible pet ownership ($p=0.0035$), and attitude toward rabies ($p=0.0109$). A study carried out in Bulacan, Philippines, revealed that men are more knowledgeable and aware of the Anti-Rabies Act than women are. This indicates that there is a gender difference in the amount of information that people know about the law and preventive measures against rabies (Dizon et al., 2022). Likewise, different research on rabies awareness discovered that men were generally more knowledgeable about national rabies law than women were, and it was suggested that specialized education could help close the knowledge gap (Hagos et al., 2020). Conversely, a study conducted in Bohol, Philippines, found that women had a higher understanding and knowledge score than men about the country's rabies law and prevention measures (Dalvin et al., 2013). Additionally, a different study that focused on Bicol, Philippines, discovered that female participants had a greater understanding of rabies regulations, preventive measures, and post-implementation than male participants. Sex is one of the demographic elements that affect people's knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors regarding proper pet keeping. It was discovered that women are more knowledgeable about pet ownership and have a more positive attitude than men (San Jose et al., 2020). Responsible pet ownership, including vaccination, breeding control, routine veterinary visits, appropriate pet housing, and other rabies prevention and management techniques, was more likely to be engaged in and acknowledged by women. This may be because of the traditional gender roles where women are often in the role of being the primary caregiver not just to children, but also to pets. This role may extend to a higher responsibility for pet welfare which leads to having improved knowledge and awareness in practices of daily pet care management (Forrest et al., 2023). On the other hand, sex is also significantly associated with attitude toward rabies. When it came to rabies prevention and management measures, women generally showed more positive attitudes than men did. This included being more willing to register their pets and being more likely to follow advised practices, like getting medical attention after an incidence of animal bites. These behaviors reflect or indicate an increasingly proactive and responsible approach to rabies prevention measures (Hagos et al., 2020).

The results showed that **Barangay** has a significant difference ($p=0.0001$) in all the variables, Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices. There were differences in the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of barangays in rural and urban areas about rabies prevention and management. It was found that urban residents had better accessibility to healthcare resources and information, which is generally a significant advantage to them resulting in greater awareness and better preventive measures against rabies as opposed to rural areas. Rabies control interventions and campaigns were concentrated in urban regions and were less common in rural barangays, which was the reason for the discrepancy between urban and rural barangays (Subedi et al., 2023; Sambo et al., 2014)

Educational attainment has a significant difference with knowledge of rabies ($p=0.0300$), knowledge of rabies law ($p=0.0001$), attitude toward responsible pet ownership ($p=0.0001$), and practices on responsible pet ownership ($p=0.0465$). Knowledge among pet owners is also significantly influenced by educational attainment. It was also highlighted that residents in urban areas with higher educational attainment demonstrated greater comprehension and adherence to the Anti-Rabies Act in the Philippines. It was found that the higher the educational attainment, the higher and better the knowledge of Rabies Law is. This is also because people with higher educational backgrounds are more likely to participate in community programs and public health initiatives aimed at managing rabies prevention and control. They also have better access to information and resources, a deeper comprehension of complex issues like laws, and improved critical thinking abilities. Along with this, having a higher educational attainment also reflects to positive attitude and practices towards responsible pet ownership. Individuals with higher educational attainment displayed better awareness and adherence to all the protocols, and responsible pet ownership guidelines to properly engage in rabies prevention control and management such as regular vaccination, proper feeding, and preventing pets from roaming around freely. (San Jose et al., 2019).

Furthermore, **monthly income** plays an important role because it also has a significant difference ($p=0.0001$) with knowledge of rabies, knowledge of rabies law, knowledge of responsible pet ownership, attitude on rabies, attitude on responsible pet ownership, practice on responsible dog ownership, practice on responsible cat ownership ($p=0.0023$), and practice on responsible pet ownership ($p=0.0003$). The study revealed a correlation between an individual's monthly income and their level of knowledge, attitude, and practices regarding rabies prevention and management. This is because individuals with higher incomes are more likely to adopt good preventive practices. After all, they can afford health services and educational materials, as well as have greater access to resources like proper medical treatment. Improved access to resources and information is made possible by financial stability, which makes it harder for individuals with low monthly incomes to adopt improved rabies prevention methods (Hagos et al., 2020).

Moreover, the **number of pets** has a significant difference to all the variables. It is significantly different ($p=0.0001$) to knowledge of rabies, knowledge of rabies law, knowledge of responsible pet ownership, attitude on rabies, practice on responsible dog ownership, ($p=0.0013$) attitude on responsible pet ownership, ($p=0.0351$) practice on responsible cat ownership, and ($p=0.0002$) practice on responsible pet ownership. Higher knowledge scores, as well as positive attitudes and actions regarding rabies prevention and management, were generally seen in households with more pets. Due to a higher sense of risk of rabies exposure from their numerous pets, they are more likely to participate in various rabies prevention and control programs and put preventive measures in place. People who owned several animals were more aware of the need for routine vaccinations and other preventative measures. This suggests a direct relationship between the number of pets owned and proactive approaches to preventive care (Dizon et al., 2022).

History of animal bites also has a significant difference ($p=0.0161$) with knowledge of rabies, ($p=0.0055$) attitude on rabies, ($p=0.0004$) knowledge on rabies law, ($p=0.0031$) attitude on responsible pet ownership, ($p=0.0195$) practice on responsible dog ownership, and ($p=0.0011$) practice on pet ownership. People with a history of animal bites demonstrated noticeably greater awareness of rabies, including the significance of post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) and the need to seek medical attention following an animal bite incident. These individuals were also more motivated to increase their knowledge and awareness of rabies symptoms, transmission, and preventive measures. This encourages the person to adopt better management and preventative techniques for rabies (Hagos et al., 2020).

Lastly, **attended awareness** activity on rabies has a significant difference with ($p=0.0005$) attitude on rabies, ($p=0.0120$) knowledge on rabies law, ($p<0.0001$) knowledge on responsible pet ownership, and practice on responsible cat ownership. People who have participated in rabies awareness programs typically know considerably more about responsible pet ownership, rabies legislation, and practices than those who have not participated. These kinds of seminars improved the knowledge of participants about legal requirements for pets, the transmission of rabies, and other preventive measures. This showed that education effectively bridged the gap in this public health risk by increasing legal knowledge as well as instilling a sense of responsibility as pet owners (Hagos et al., 2020).

Relationship of the respondent's level of knowledge, attitude, and practices on rabies prevention and management

Relationships were tested among the participants' knowledge, attitude, and practices. A significant relationship with **knowledge on rabies** was found with all the variables expected in practice in responsible pet ownership. It was discovered that there is a strong relationship between general rabies knowledge and knowledge of rabies law. It was discovered that people with a far deeper comprehension and awareness of rabies were also more likely to be aware of and comprehend the Anti-Rabies Act's provisions better. This implies that the more people know about rabies, the more people know about rabies law. This was also linked to a favorable viewpoint on rabies prevention efforts. Knowledgeable people are more inclined to adhere to and support preventive measures like vaccinating dogs and restricting their freedom of movement. It also has a direct impact on improved cat and dog ownership habits. A greater understanding of rabies influences how pet owners care for their animals and adhere to regulations meant to stop the disease from spreading (Iddi et al., 2023; Hagos et al., 2020)

A stronger knowledge of responsible pet ownership was substantially correlated with a higher understanding of **rabies law**. People who knew the rules and regulations were more likely to recognize the significance of pet health and immunization. Additionally, research revealed a significant correlation between knowledge of rabies law and attitudes toward preventing rabies. Those with this knowledge were more inclined to favor policies like regulating the number of stay dogs and to acknowledge the crucial role that laws play in preventing rabies. Furthermore, it has a strong correlation

with responsible dog and cat ownership behaviors, as these people were more likely to participate in various programs and protocols (Hagos et al., 2020; San Jose et al., 2020). This demonstrated how legal knowledge had a direct impact on practical pet care measures. It not only increases understanding of ethical pet ownership but also encourages pet owners to adopt positive attitudes and behaviors. This suggests that enhancing public health outcomes related to rabies requires legal education.

Moreover, **knowledge on responsible pet ownership** has a significant relationship with attitude on rabies, attitude on responsible pet ownership, practice on responsible dog ownership, practice on responsible cat ownership, and practice on responsible pet ownership. Higher awareness about responsible pet ownership was associated with a more positive attitude toward rabies prevention, according to a study done in Magalang, Pampanga. This association implies that knowing appropriate pet ownership, which includes various preventative techniques and routine vaccination, can encourage a more proactive approach to rabies prevention. Furthermore, a high level of pet ownership knowledge was also associated with a significant inclination to participate in various programs or activities that promote actively involved and effective methods for controlling and preventing rabies. In essence, this enhances pet management procedures, including basic care and compliance with regulations (San Jose et al., 2020).

It was discovered that a positive **attitude toward rabies and an attitude toward responsible pet ownership** were strongly correlated with a practice of responsible dog ownership and responsible pet ownership activities. Positivity increased the likelihood of responsible ownership; those with positive attitudes were also more likely to recognize and follow advice on appropriate pet management, including vaccinations, restricting pets, and taking responsibility for their care. This correlation demonstrates how crucial positive involvement is for improving compliance and managing diseases effectively (Dizon et al., 2022). Nevertheless, the noteworthy correlation is not equally strong when it comes to appropriate cat-owning practices. This might be because dogs and cats have different practical requirements when it comes to pet ownership. Given the higher incidence of rabies in dogs than in cats, dogs are generally seen as more dangerous than cats and as needing tight ownership guidelines. It's common to view cats as less dangerous for rabies exposure and transmission, and as needing less strict supervision. This may be the cause of their lack of equal attention to responsible ownership practices (Hagos et al., 2020).

Conclusions

This study investigated the knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to rabies virus exposure prevention and management among the residents in San Fernando, Pampanga. Also, the study assessed the contribution of the demographic profile of the participants to their level of knowledge, attitudes, and practices.

The majority of the respondents are aged 25 to 34 years old, male, high school graduates, with a lower income of below Php 10,000 to Php 19,999 monthly. Most of the

respondents own 2 pets, have at least one (1) family member who has been bitten by an animal, and have also attended an awareness seminar on rabies. Likewise, the majority came from Barangay Calulut, with a total of 47 respondents. The result showed that the majority of the respondents answered school as their source of knowledge which can then indicate that facilitating more rabies prevention and control programs can strengthen the knowledge of individuals which can be a big help in addressing this public health concern. Additionally, almost 70% have at least one (1) family member who has been bitten by an animal. This high incident rate revealed that there are still a lot of people who lack a positive attitude and appropriate practices regarding their responsibility as pet owners. This indicates the urgent need for comprehensive public health education focusing on rabies prevention and management. It is crucial to enhance targeted educational campaigns especially concerning responsible pet ownership while considering different factors that can influence their knowledge, attitude, and practices.

In concluding this study, for the second objective, it was found that only 12% have good knowledge, 49% have fair knowledge, and 39% have low knowledge of rabies. Moreover, the majority of them believe that rabies is not caused by a virus, which is incorrect. Furthermore, most of them said that cats can be rabid and also believe that bats can be a source of rabies, but most of them said that snakes cannot be a source of rabies, which were all correct answers. In the same manner, a considerable number of the respondents were also incorrect in realizing that rabies can be acquired through inhalations, bites of mosquitoes or other insects, and by eating the meat of dogs with rabies. But above all, the majority of them believe that rabies can be acquired by animals and humans through the bite of an animal with rabies, and they also believe that it can be acquired when licked or scratched by an animal with rabies. Aside from this, it was also revealed that the majority of the respondents (70.75%) have a low level of knowledge when it comes to rabies law and only 15.75% have a good level of knowledge which indicates a significant need to increase awareness of everyone not only about rabies itself but also about the laws and regulations that talks about rabies. Moreover, knowledge on responsible pet ownership has a quite good result because the majority have a good level of knowledge which is 47.25%, but still the percentage did not even reach half of it, therefore, the need to increase knowledge and awareness when it comes to pet ownership is still significant

Conversely, most of them had a good or positive attitude toward rabies. In other ways, the majority of the respondents said that they would inform authorities and get medical treatment if bitten by a stray dog or cat. Likewise, most of them said that they would not kill a stray dog/cat suspected of having rabies. More than 70% also believe it is important to stop the dog population from growing and that they are willing to help the campaign against rabies.

Other than that, practices on pet ownership among dog owners all have relationships based on knowledge and attitudes, with all relationships being positive. This means that having higher knowledge and attitudes about rabies corresponds to higher practice. In the practice of cat owners, there is only a significant association with knowledge, with knowledge of responsible ownership having a negative relationship.

Foregrounding 70% of the respondents who mostly said that they got bitten (1) by an animal, compared to dog owners, cat owners have poorer pet care practices; most do not vaccinate their cats and allow them to wander freely. Furthermore, most don't have a record of their pet's vaccinations. When asked why they do not vaccinate their cats, the majority of them said that they can't touch their pets, that they don't know the vaccination schedule, that their pet isn't at home or out and about when the vaccinator arrives, and that they don't know when to vaccinate their pets.

After assessing the association between the demographic variables of the respondents and the knowledge, attitude, and practice level on rabies virus prevention and management, it was revealed that almost all the variables (age, sex, barangay, educational attainment, monthly income, number of pets, history of an animal bite, and attended awareness activity on rabies) have a significant difference with their level of knowledge, attitude, and practices ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, the first null hypothesis is rejected.

In terms of assessing the relationship between knowledge, attitude, and practices on rabies prevention and management, it was revealed that almost all of the variables are correlated with each other. Hence, the second null hypothesis is rejected.

Recommendations

As established in this study, it cannot be denied that the public still has misconceptions about rabies virus prevention and management. Thus, the researchers recommend the following to address the significant results for each objective:

Level of Knowledge on Rabies Prevention and Management. Based on the results, it was revealed that the respondents have a significantly low level of knowledge on rabies in general, and also when it comes to rabies law. By this, it is recommended to increase and strengthen the educational awareness campaigns that talk about rabies, specifically on rabies law, as well as on responsible pet ownership. It is recommended to widen the scope of the campaigns and not only limit it to Barangay or community seminars. Provide campaigns particularly in schools since it was found out on results that schools are the majority's source of reliable information. Additionally, maximize the use of other platforms that will serve as their source of knowledge such as television, radio, newspaper, magazines, and other accessible platforms to disseminate information regarding rabies prevention and management.

Level of Attitude on Rabies Prevention and Management. Knowledge can be reflected or applied to one's attitude. By this, it is recommended to emphasize the recommended management of responsible pet ownership, as well as the importance of seeking help from the authorities and medical professionals if incidents like animal bites happen. It is also recommended to emphasize the importance of having their pets vaccinated regularly for anti-rabies because based on the results, it was found that some of the respondents will only vaccinate their pets when it is free from charge.

Level of Practices on Rabies Prevention and Management. Based on the result, it showed a positive or good level of practice, especially in dog ownership. However, the results also revealed a low to fair level of practices when it comes to cat ownership. By this, it is recommended to have a fair level of emphasis on cats and dogs when having educational campaigns on rabies prevention and management. Emphasize the importance of responsible cat ownership as well so their level of knowledge, attitude, and practices on cat ownership will not be left behind, because cats can also be a source of rabies.

Differences of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices based on Demographic Characteristics. It is recommended to develop targeted educational campaigns on rabies prevention tailored to different demographics within the community. Consider age, sex, language, cultural background, literacy levels, and other demographic factors when designing materials and messaging. Also, Prioritize education in barangays with lower knowledge scores. Tailor programs to specific misconceptions and knowledge gaps identified in the survey.

Significant Relationship between the Level of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices in Rabies Prevention and Management. KAP is reported to have a significant relationship with one another, therefore, it is recommended to ensure providing accessible resources to the community that will emphasize the importance of having sufficient knowledge and awareness, as well as demonstrating positive attitude and practices towards rabies prevention and management.

The researchers also recommend their results to the following:

General Public. Based on the results, the public may be made more aware of the proper practices on how to prevent the rabies virus. By this, it is recommended to ensure pets, especially dogs and cats, are up-to-date on their rabies vaccinations. Thus, vaccinating pets not only protects them but also prevents the spread of rabies to humans. In addition, include information about rabies prevention and management in community emergency preparedness plans. By this, it ensures that protocols are in place for responding to rabies incidents effectively

Future researchers. Future researchers on a related topic are recommended to expand the scope of their investigations by focusing on new provinces or regions to further this study. To determine whether precise categories for each demographic category explicitly correlate with the respondents' knowledge and habits, more research is also required. It is also recommended to investigate or explore deeper on the difference between dog and cat ownership to determine the possible factors of having such discrepancy.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study underwent review and evaluation by the University of the Assumption Ethics Review Board (UAREB) before the data-gathering procedure. The UAREB was

provided with copies of the required documents including the research manuscript, informed consent, and the survey questionnaire.

REFERENCES

- Bundalian, R. J. D., Lacson, M. B., Magsino, P. J. P., Bacani, C., Soriano, D. R., Garing, A., Aquino, A. J., Policarpio, A., Mallari, J. K., San Jose, R., Bulao, M. F., & Tangquilut, N. (2020). A Study on Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices on Rabies in the Philippines. *Kesmas: Jurnal Kesehatan Masyarakat Nasional (National Public Health Journal)*.
<https://scholarhub.ui.ac.id/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1604&context=kesmas>
- Claude Sabeta., et al. —Limitations of Diagnostic Tests Using Rabies as an Example. *EC Veterinary Science* 6.6 (2022): 60-63
- Dizon TJR, Saito N, Inobaya M, Tan A, Reñosa MDC, Bravo TA, et al. (2022) Household survey on owned dog population and rabies knowledge in selected municipalities in Bulacan, Philippines: A cross-sectional study. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis* 16(1): e0009948. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0009948
- Forrest, R., Pearson, M., & Awawdeh, L. (2023). Pet Owners' Attitudes and Opinions towards Cat and Dog Care Practices in Aotearoa New Zealand. *Veterinary Sciences*, 10(10), 606. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vetsci10100606>
- Hagos, W. G., Muchie, K. F., Gebru, G. G., Mezgebe, G. G., Reda, K. A., & Dachew, B. A. (2020, January 14). Assessment of knowledge, attitude and practice towards rabies and associated factors among household heads in Mekelle City, Ethiopia - *BMC Public Health*. *BioMed Central*. <https://bmcpublihealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889-020-8145-7#>
- Hampson, K.; Coudeville, L.; Lembo, T.; Sambo, M.; Kieffer, A.; Atlan, M.; Barrat, J.; Blanton, J.D.; Briggs, D.J.; Cleaveland, S.; et al. Estimating the global burden of endemic canine rabies. *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 2015, 9, e0003709. [Google Scholar]
- Herbert, M.; Riyaz Basha, S.; Thangaraj, S. Community perception regarding rabies prevention and stray dog control in urban slums in India. *J. Infect. Public Health* 2012, 5, 374–380. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef] [PubMed]
- Hergert, M.; Nel, L.H. Dog bite histories and response to incidents in canine rabies enzootic KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 2013, 7, e2059. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef] [PubMed]
- Iddi, S., Mlenga, F., Hamasaki, K., Mwita, S., & Konje, E. (n.d.). Assessment of knowledge, attitude, and practice of dog owners to rabies disease in Kahama Town Council, Shinyanga Region, Tanzania. *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases*
- Jemberu WT, Molla W, Almaw G, Alemu S. Incidence of rabies in humans and domestic animals and people's awareness in North Gondar Zone, Ethiopia. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis.* 2013 May 9;7(5):e2216. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0002216. PMID: 23675547; PMCID: PMC3649954.
- Kumarapeli, V., & De Silva, S. (2021, October 8). (PDF) Responsible Dog Ownership: Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices of adults residing in a semi-urban Medical

- Officer of Health area in Sri Lanka. ResearchGate. Retrieved May 27, 2024, from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/355144451>
- Lankester, F.; Hampson, K.; Lembo, T.; Palmer, G.; Taylor, L. Infectious diseases: implementing Pasteur's vision for rabies elimination. *Science* 2014, 345, 1562–1564. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef] [PubMed]
- Lembo, T.; Hampson, K.; Kaare, M.T.; Ernest, E.; Knobel, D.; Kazwala, R.R.; Haydon, D.T.; Cleaveland, S. The feasibility of canine rabies elimination in Africa: dispelling doubts with data. *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 2010, 4, e626. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef] [PubMed]
- Leung A.K.C., HD D., KLE H. Rabies: epidemiology, pathogenesis, and prophylaxis. *Adv. Ther.* 2007;24(6):1340–1347. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
- Meslin F., Briggs D.J. Eliminating canine rabies, the principal source of human infection: what will it take? *Antivir. Res.* 2013;98(2):291–296. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
- Miranda L.M., Miranda M.E., Hatch B., Deray R., Shwiff S., Roces M.C., Rupprecht C.E. Towards canine rabies elimination in Cebu, Philippines: assessment of health economic data. *Transboundary Emerg. Dis.* 2017;64(1):121–129. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
- OIE ASEAN Rabies Elimination Strategy 2016. <https://asean.org/storage/2017/02> [Google Scholar]
- Pushkar Pal., Yawongsa, A., Bhusal, T. N., Bashyal, R., & Rukkwamsuk, T. (2021, April). Knowledge, attitude, and practice about rabies prevention and Control: A Community Survey in Nepal. *Veterinary world.* <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8167543/>
- Rabies Prevention and Control (2024, May 13). Rabies. <https://www.cdc.gov/rabies/about/index.html>
- Rabies Prevention and Control Program. 2016. <http://www.doh.gov.ph/national>
- Republic of the Philippines-13th Congress. 2007. Republic Act 9482: Anti-Rabies Act of 2007.: <http://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/downloads/2007/05may/20070525>
- Salahuddin, N.; Gohar, M.A.; Baig-Ansari, N. Reducing cost of rabies post-exposure prophylaxis: experience of a tertiary care hospital in Pakistan. *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 2016, 10, e0004448. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef] [PubMed]
- Salomao C, Nacima A, Cuamba L, Gujral L, Amiel O, Baltazar C, et al. Epidemiology, clinical features and risk factors for human rabies and animal bites during an outbreak of rabies in Maputo and Matola cities, Mozambique, 2014: Implications for public health interventions for rabies control. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis* 2017 Jul;11(7): e0005787. pmid:28742094
- Sambo, M., Lembo, T., Cleaveland, S., Ferguson, H. M., Sikana, L., Simon, C., Urassa, H., & Hampson, K. (n.d.). Knowledge, attitudes and practices (KAP) about rabies prevention and Control: A Community Survey in Tanzania. *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases.* <https://journals.plos.org/plosntds/article?id=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0003310>
- San Jose, R., Magsino, P. J., & Bundalian, R. (2019, May 21). Pet owners' awareness on RA 9482 (Anti-Rabies Act of 2007) in Magalang, Pampanga Philippines. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6529737>
- Smith, L. M., Quinnell, R., Munteanu, A., Hartmann, S., Villa, P. D., & Collins, L. (n.d.).

- Attitudes towards free-roaming dogs and dog ownership practices in Bulgaria, Italy, and Ukraine. PLOS ONE. <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371%2F>
- Subedi, S., Adhikari, K., Regmi, D., Sharma, H. K., Bolakhe, N., Kandel, M., & Subedi, D. (2023, August 11). Assessment of community knowledge and practices towards rabies prevention: A cross-sectional survey in Bharatpur, Chitwan, Nepal. MDPI. <https://www.mdpi.com/2813-0227/3/3/17#metrics>
- Taylor LH, Wallace RM, Balaram D, Lindenmayer JM, Eckery DC, Mutoono-Watkiss B, Parravani E, Nel LH. The Role of Dog Population Management in Rabies Elimination-A Review of Current Approaches and Future Opportunities. *Front Vet Sci.* 2017 Jul 10;4:109. doi: 10.3389/fvets.2017.00109. PMID: 28740850; PMCID: PMC5502273.
- Tripathy, R. M., Satapathy, S. P., & Karmee, N. (2017). Assessment of knowledge, attitude and practice regarding rabies and its prevention among construction workers: a cross-sectional study in Berhampur, Odisha. *International Journal of Research in Medical Sciences*, 5(9), 3971–3975. <https://doi.org/10.18203/2320-6012.ijrms20173964>
- WHO Guide for Rabies Pre and post Exposure Prophylaxis in Humans https://www.who.int/rabies/PEP_prophylaxis_guidelines_June10pdf (2010)
- World Health Organization. 2012. Strategic Framework for Elimination of Human Rabies Transmitted by Dogs in the South-East Asia Region. Available online: http://www.searo.who.int/entity/emerging_diseases/links/Zoonos